

Employing a synthesized pyrazole derivative for selectively visible detection of fluoride ion and its explanation by theoretical calculations

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Here we have designed and synthesized a new Schiff base biologically active pyrazole derivative 5-methyl-*N'*-(1-((naphthalen-2-yl)methyl)-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene)-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carbohydrazide (PYNAP, containing -C=O and -NH group) used for selective sensing of fluoride ions. PYNAP has been characterized by ¹H NMR, IR spectroscopy, HRMS spectrometry and elemental analysis. Fluoride ion selectivity of PYNAP has been observed by involvement of -NH proton with -C=O group in the probe to form imidol which is responsible for H-bonding interaction with F⁻. Through H-bonding interaction, imidol form of PYNAP interacted with F⁻ and the binding stoichiometry (1:2) has been confirmed by Job's plot, HRMS spectral studies and ¹H NMR analysis. PYNAP possess sensing ability of F⁻ by changing the colour from yellow to red. Sensing mechanism was ascribed to the intramolecular proton transfer from -NH group to keto group of PYNAP which originates H-bonding interaction with F⁻. In addition, the ground state geometry of PYNAP has been optimized by density functional theory. The theoretical results have also supported the selective sensing of PYNAP towards F⁻ in presence of other anions.

Keywords: Synthesis, fluoride sensing, H-bonding interaction, DFT.

Introduction

Immense challenge for researcher is anion sensing due to its importance in biological, chemical, industrial and environmental field^{1,2}. Here we have drawn a scheme for fluoride ion recognition among different types of anions. Fluoride ion is extremely toxic and very harmful to living beings. Hydroxyl group containing proteins, enzyme and DNA interact with fluoride ion and damage the activity of living cell. Therefore fluoride ion is harmful for the enzymatic activity and influences on many biological function which leads to many health disorder. However, excessive accumulation of fluoride anion in human body causes several serious diseases such as bone disorder (fluorosis)³, collagen breakdown⁴, depression of thyroid activity⁵ and disruption of immune systems⁶. In addition fluoride contamination causes a serious environmental anxiety throughout the world and has wide-ranging impact in the lithosphere and in water^{7,8}.

Now a days, there are significant advances in the design and synthesis of probes for fluoride ion detection, and many of them are suitable for biological applications in living cell systems. The typical F⁻ ion sensing PYNAP molecule contains pyrazol moiety. Pyrazol moiety is one of the essential

classes of N-containing heterocycles and extensively used as key building blocks for pharmaceutical agents. Moreover it exhibits a wide spectrum of pharmacophore such as antimicrobial⁹, analgesic¹⁰, fungicidal¹¹ and anti-inflammatory¹² agents.

Generally there are different types of interaction of ligand with anions such as hydrogen-bonding interactions, Lewis acid-base interactions, anion- π interactions and anion induced chemical reactions¹³⁻¹⁵. Here fluoride induced chemical reaction is responsible for the structural change of the ligand and significant for high sensitivity and selectivity.

In this present study, we have synthesized pyrazol based Schiff base ligand 5-methyl-*N'*-(1-((naphthalen-yl)methyl)-2-oxoindolin-3-ylidene)-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carbohydrazide (PYNAP) as a new chemosensor for the detection of fluoride ion. It has shown high selectivity and sensitivity to F⁻ over other competitive anions, on the basis of weak H-bonding interaction between PYNAP with F⁻. Anion-receptor interactions involve the charge rearrangement in the system which has influence on the structure of PYNAP. This weak H-bonding interaction has been confirmed by different experimental techniques like absorbance, ¹H NMR titration and HRMS

spectroscopic studies. In addition the structure of PYNAP has been optimized by density functional theory (DFT) to compare with experimental findings.

Experimental

Materials:

The spectral grade solvents methanol (MeOH), ethanol (EtOH), dimethyl formamide (DMF), glacial acetic acid, acetone were purchased from E. Merck, India. Indoline-2,3-dione, 2-(bromomethyl)naphthalene, diethyl oxalate, cesium carbonate and hydrazine hydrate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. Solvents were purified and dried according to standard method described elsewhere¹⁶. Tetrabutylammonium salts of F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , $H_2PO_4^-$, AcO^- , ClO_4^- , CN^- , SCN^- and HSO_4^- were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and sodium carbonate and sodium sulphate were procured from commercial sources and all were used as received. Millipore water was used throughout the experiments. DMSO- d_6 and $CDCl_3$ were used for NMR experiments as received from Sigma-Aldrich, USA.

Method:

1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained from a Bruker Avance DPX 300 spectrometer using DMSO- d_6 and $CDCl_3$ solution. Infrared spectra ($4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were taken on KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer Spectrum BX-II IR spectrometer. Mass spectroscopic analysis of the ligand was performed in a QTOF Micro YA263 ESI-TOF mass spectrometer using methanol as solvent. Elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed with a Perkin-Elmer CHN analyzer 2400. Absorption spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu (model UV1700) UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Ground state geometries of PYNAP was optimized employing density functional theory^{17,18} using the B3LYP^{19,20} functional with the standard basis set, 6-311G(d,p), for all atoms in the Gaussian 09 program²¹.

Synthetic procedure of PYNAP:

Synthesis of compound NAPISA:

Indoline-2,3-dione (1 g, 6.79 mmol) was dissolved in DMF (15 mL) and treated with cesium carbonate (3.54 g, 10.86 mmol) and 2-(bromomethyl)naphthalene (1.99 g, 9.03 mmol). The mixture was stirred at ambient temperature for 2 days. The reaction mixture was quenched with ice and then, extracted with ethyl acetate and finally washed with brine (100

mL \times 3), then dried over sodium sulphate under reduced pressure to give an orange solid product. Yield: 0.8 g, 40%; 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ (ppm): 5.10 (2H, s, $-CH_2-$), 6.82 (1H, d, naph-H, J 7.9 Hz), 7.09 (1H, d, Ar-H, J 5 Hz), 7.50–7.42 (4H, m, naph-H and Ar-H), 7.63 (1H, d, naph-H, J 7.3 Hz), 7.85–7.79 (4H, m, naph-H and Ar-H) (Fig. S1); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 400–4000: ν : 3447, 2924, 2364, 1729, 1607, 1465, 1338, 1171, 1089, 1022, 862, 812, 753, 466 (Fig. S2); Anal. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{13}NO_2$: C, 79.53; H, 4.58; N, 4.89. Found: C, 79.43; H, 4.56; N, 4.88.

Synthesis of compound PYHD:

5-Methyl-1H-pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid hydrazide (PYHD) was prepared according to the literature procedure²² as described previously and was characterized by 1H NMR, mass data and FT-IR.

Synthesis of compound PYNAP:

PYHD (0.2 g, 1.427 mmol) was dissolved in 10 ml methanol and stirred rapidly with mild heating. To this NAPISA (0.410 g, 1.427 mmol) was added slowly along with a drop of glacial acetic acid. The solution was brought to reflux and continued for 6 h, followed by cooling to obtain a yellow precipitate which was filtered under suction, washed with cold methanol and dried under vacuum overnight. Yield: 0.35 g, 60%; 1H NMR in DMSO- d_6 , 500 MHz, δ (ppm): 14.04 (1H, s, $-CONH-$), 13.33 (1H, s, $-NH-$), 7.89–7.96 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.67 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.49–7.55 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.37 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.15 (1H, d, Ar-H), 7.08 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar-H), 6.65 (1H, s, Py-H), 5.18 (2H, s, $-N-CH_2-$ naph), 2.37 (3H, s, Py- CH_3) (Fig. S3); ESI-MS: m/z calculated for $C_{24}H_{19}N_5O_2$ $[M+H]^+$ 410.15, Found 410.05 (Fig. S4); Anal. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{19}N_5O_2$: C, 70.41; H, 4.73; N, 17.08. Found: C, 70.40; H, 4.68; N, 17.10%; ^{13}C NMR in (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ (ppm): 10.42, 105.35, 110.44, 119.78, 120.71, 123.29, 125.58, 126.05, 126.18, 126.48, 127.74, 128.57, 131.34, 132.44, 132.93, 133.31, 136.91, 141.10, 142.70, 144.94, 160.97 (Fig. S5).

Results and discussion

Absorbance study:

The absorption spectra of PYNAP have been recorded at around 334 nm in DMF solvent corresponding to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the molecule. The anion recognition property of the ligand PYNAP was carried out by monitoring UV-Vis spectral properties in the presence of different anions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , $H_2PO_4^-$, AcO^- , ClO_4^- , SCN^- , CN^- and HSO_4^- , as

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the probe PYNAP.

their tetrabutyl ammonium salts) in DMF solution. No spectral change of PYNAP has been occurred with the addition of all above said ions except F^- (shown in bar diagram Fig. 1). The absorbance of PYNAP decreased at 334 nm with the addition of F^- ions upto 68.1 mM and simultaneously a new peak generated at about 400–405 nm (Fig. 1). It indicates that ground state interaction takes place between PYNAP and F^- ions. From the absorbance profile of PYNAP it has been seen that a new complex is formed which absorbs at 405 nm.

Fig. 1. (a) Absorption spectra of PYNAP upon addition of F^- ions upto 68.1 mM (Inset figure shows the zoom part of increasing absorbance of PYNAP upon addition of F^- ions upto 68.1 mM) and (b) bar diagram represent the selectivity of PYNAP towards F^- ions over the various anions.

Developing of a newly formed peak at 405 nm indicates that imidol formation takes place from the amide by the F^- induced chemical reaction and also imidol form of PYNAP is stabilised by the interaction of F^- through intermolecular H-bonding. The Limit of Detection (LOD) of F^- by PYNAP has

been calculated by the 3σ method²³ ($LOD = 3\sigma/m$ where ' σ ' and ' m ' are the standard deviation of blank (0.01279) and the slope of the absorbance vs concentration of F^- plot respectively, and the value is 1.11×10^{-4} (M). Consequently, from absorbance it has been found that PYNAP can sense F^- as low as 1.11×10^{-4} (M) concentration.

Binding constant and stoichiometry: Absorbance studies were used for the determination of binding constant values between PYNAP and F^- using the following Benesi-Hildebrand (B-H) equation²⁴ (eq. (1)).

$$\frac{1}{I_a - I_{a0}} = \frac{1}{I_{a1} - I_{a0}} - \frac{1}{K(I_{a1} - I_{a0})[F^-]^2} \quad (1)$$

where K is the binding constant I_{a0} is the initial absorbance of free host, I_a is the intermediate absorbance of PYNAP: F^- and I_{a1} is the maximum absorbance of the PYNAP: F^- adduct formed. A plot of $\frac{1}{I_a - I_{a0}}$ vs $\frac{1}{[F^-]^2}$ provides a straight line throughout the entire range of F^- concentration (Fig. 2a) indicating 1:2 adduct. Binding constant of the complex formed is $2.4 \times 10^4 M^{-1}$.

To establish the binding ratio between PYNAP and F^- using absorbance values from Job's plot (Fig. 2b), it was found that, intensity minima was observed at 0.6 mole fraction, indicating that the PYNAP forms 1:2 complex with F^- through weak intermolecular hydrogen bonding interaction. It has been further confirmed by ESI mass spectra of the complex in methanol solvent. ESI mass spectral peak at $m/z = 448.0013$ also supported the 1:2 stoichiometry of the PYNAP: F^- complex (Fig. S6). The binding ratio, ESI mass spectra and IR spectra of the complex (Fig. S7) indicate that imidol form of PYNAP interact with two F^- ions through H-bonding²⁵.

Fig. 2. (a) B-H plot from the absorption spectra of PYNAP with F^- ions and (b) Job's plot of PYNAP with F^- ions from the absorption spectra.

^1H and ^{13}C NMR titrations:

We have carried out ^1H NMR studies for the confirmation of imidol from amide with addition of F^- to PYNAP and the possible binding interaction site between imidol form of PYNAP and F^- in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$. ^1H NMR spectra of PYNAP has been changed after the addition of F^- ions. In absence of F^- ions, $\text{N}-\text{H}_a$ and $\text{N}-\text{H}_b$ protons of PYNAP appeared at 14.03 ppm and 13.32 ppm respectively (Fig. 3). H_a and H_b protons moved out after addition of F^- ions. This disappearance of H_a and H_b protons clearly indicate the involvement of $-\text{NH}$ proton into $-\text{CO}$ group through extended conjugation of PYNAP to satisfy the hydrogen bonding interaction with F^- ions. Hydrogen bonding interaction between PYNAP and F^- affects the electronic environment of all the protons of PYNAP in ^1H NMR spectra.

Fig. 3. ^1H NMR spectra of (a) PYNAP and (b) PYNAP with F^- ions.

To support ^1H NMR observation, ^{13}C NMR spectra has been recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solvent. Carbonyl carbon peak for free PYNAP are 166 ppm (a) and 158 ppm (b) respectively. With addition of F^- ion to PYNAP, the carbonyl carbon peak shifted from 166 ppm to 144 ppm and 158 ppm to 135 ppm respectively. This upfield shift observation can be explained on the basis of increasing electron density caused by F^- interaction^{26,27}. This experiment also indicates that the interaction takes place between imidol form of PYNAP and F^- ions through H bonding (Fig. 4).

Colorimetric experiments:

PYNAP solution shows yellow colour in naked-eye. Colour of PYNAP solution has been changed from yellow to red with

Fig. 4. ^{13}C NMR spectra of (a) PYNAP and (b) PYNAP with F^- ions.

addition of F^- ions. But no change of colour of PYNAP is observed in the presence of other ions such as Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , H_2PO_4^- , AcO^- , ClO_4^- , CN^- , SCN^- and HSO_4^- which can be easily distinguished by the naked-eye as can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Change in colour of PYNAP upon addition of different anions.

pH titration:

For confirmation of H-bonding interaction between imidol form of PYNAP and F^- ion pH titration was carried out. There is no spectral change of PYNAP in low pH whereas a new peak generated at 405 nm with the addition of 0.05 M NaOH solutions up to pH 11.5 which is similar to the addition of F^- to PYNAP (Fig. S8). A new peak at 405 nm in high pH indicates that amide form of PYNAP is converted into imidol form by deprotonating of $-\text{NH}$ proton in basic media. Further addition of H^+ to PYNAP, new peak at 405 nm vanished and PYNAP could be recyclable. This observation supports that binding interaction between imidol form of PYNAP and F^- can be attributed through hydrogen bonding by deprotonation of $-\text{NH}$ proton. From ^1H NMR titration one can say that deprotonation of $-\text{NH}$ proton of PYNAP due to addition of F^- ion supports H-bonding interaction. The result of pH titration

also supports the absorbance, ESI-mass and ^1H NMR titration results.

Theoretical studies:

To verify the experimental findings of PYNAP, quantum chemical calculations were performed. In the first step ground state geometry of PYNAP was optimized. TD-DFT method was applied to determine ground state geometry as well as the transition energy and oscillator strength (f). The optimized geometrical structures with the Mulliken charge distribution (GS: -0.53 to $+0.53$) and the HOMO-LUMO energy gap of PYNAP is -3.78 eV as shown in Fig. 6. The theoretical absorbance spectra of PYNAP is 303 nm with oscillator strength 0.3964 is very close to the experimental absorbance (334 nm) value. After PYNAP optimization, PYNAP: F^- and PYNAP: X^- (X^- : other anions) have been optimized and TD-DFT method was applied for respective compound to determine the transition energy and oscillator strength (f). It has been seen that the HOMO-LUMO energy gap of free PYNAP molecule is 4.09 eV whereas energy gap for PYNAP: F^- composite is 3.11 eV. This observation indicates that PYNAP is stabilized by F^- ion interaction. On the other hand with the presence of other ions (X^-) HOMO (0.32 eV) and LUMO (1.95 eV) of PYNAP molecule are highly destabilized. The theoretical absorbance of PYNAP: F^- is at 399 nm with oscillator strength 0.6188 which is very close to the experimental absorbance (405 nm) value. So experimentally observed new peak at 405 nm is also supported by theoretical results. So the new peak at 405 nm is due to the interaction between imidol form of PYNAP and F^- . From Fig. 7 it has been observed that the electronic charge distribution of free PYNAP is different from that of PYNAP: F^- system. For PYNAP: F^-

Fig. 6. Optimization structure of PYNAP molecule with Mulliken's charge distribution for ground state and HOMO-LUMO energy gap.

Fig. 7. Molecular orbital diagram with corresponding energy levels of PYNAP, PYNAP: F^- and PYNAP: X^- (X^- : other anions) complex in GS.

Table 1. HOMO-LUMO energy gap (ΔE), oscillator strength (f), theoretical and experimental absorbance of PYNAP, PYNAP: F^- and PYNAP: X^- system (X^- : other anions)

System	ΔE (eV)	f	λ_{theo} (nm)	λ_{exp} (nm)
PYNAP	4.09	0.3964	303	334
PYNAP: F^-	3.11	0.6188	399	405
PYNAP: X^-	1.78	0.0521	697	334

system the electronic distribution is more in the interaction site which also support the up field shift of carbonyl carbon peak in ^{13}C NMR spectra. Hence the theoretical results confirm the experimental findings for selective detection of F^- only by PYNAP through H-bonding in presence of other ions.

Comparison of published F^- sensor:

There are many published articles where a series of anions were taken to find out the selection of particular anions by scheming and synthesizing of different chemosensors. Bhattacharyya *et al.* reported that AH chemosensor selectively detected F^- ion but not other anions²⁸. But they had not shown the reason of particularly F^- ions detection by AH chemosensor over other anions. Li *et al.* also reported the detection of F^- ion among series of anions by synthesizing quinoline derivative but had not shown the particular reason of detection of only F^- ion²⁹. Herein we tabulated some published articles³⁰⁻³² on F^- ion sensing, where none described the reason of detection of only F^- ions among others ions

(Table S1). But in this work, the reason of selective detection of F⁻ ion through naked-eye among other ions by proposed chemosensor has been established with theoretical investigation.

Conclusions

In this present work pyrazole derivative based Schiff base ligand PYNAP was synthesized and characterized by different spectroscopic technique. PYNAP has selective F⁻ sensing ability by its structural change. The structural change of PYNAP by addition of F⁻ has been confirmed by pH, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR titration. The binding ability and stoichiometric ratio was determined by UV-absorbance and Job's plot. In addition, the reason of selectivity of PYNAP to F⁻ ions among other anions has also been explained by DFT calculations. Theoretical results conclude that the HOMO-LUMO energy gap of PYNAP:F⁻ system is low whereas HOMO and LUMO were destabilized for PYNAP:X⁻ system. This study will help us to develop this type of chemosensor for detection of fluoride ion and applications in pharmaceutical industry.

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